
INTERMEDIATE EFFICIENCY OF TEST STATISTICS ON NONPARAMETRIC GENERALIZED RANDOM FIELD REGRESSION WITH CENSORING

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ABSTRACT

The concept of intermediate efficiency or i-efficiency as introduced by Kallenberg (1983) and later so-called pathwise variants from Ingnot, Ledwina, and Cmiel (2018), will be utilized to obtain a relative local and global measure of efficiency for test statistics on the nonparametric generalized random field regression with random censored data. We will also investigate and propose an i-efficiency for generalized quantum field regression testing with random censoring based on orthomodular lattice representations of classes of quantum probabilities and other general uncertainty frameworks for probabilities.

Introduction

Kallenberg (1983) introduced an asymptotic relative efficiency measure (ARE), the intermediate efficiency or i-efficiency (i-ARE) as an intermediate means of measuring the efficiencies of test statistics with respect to the extreme positions taken by the Pitman and Bahadur approaches respectively[6]. To this end, we introduce a generalization of his approach that puts the calculation of the i-ARE in familiar grounds with the Pitman efficiency, (i.e., as a ratio of efficiencies). More recent variants of Kallenberg i-ARE, denoted as K i-ARE, introduced by Ingnot, Ledwina and Cmiel (2018) and denoted here by ILC i-ARE will then be formed for comparing generalized regression tests. As special cases, we then utilize recent Cramer-type large deviation results for linear rank statistics and the general asymptotic results of Cezick to form the efficacy term for linear rank statistics[2]. Next we calculate the K i-ARE of the linear rank statistic with respect to some MLE test statistics for the nonparametric generalized random field regression coefficient problem with censored data. The efficacy term for the MLE test statistic will be calculated intermediately. The cases for a known population variance and estimated one will be covered. Asymptotic normality and large and moderate Cramer-type deviation are necessary for the computation of K i-ARE for the test statistics as presented here, in addition to certain asymptotic properties for Kallenberg sequences of alternatives $\{\theta_n\} \subset \Omega$, levels of significance $\{\alpha_n\}$, and distributions $f(\cdot|\theta_i)$ under the alternatives.

In an attempt to simplify the requirements and assumptions made under the development of the K i-ARE, Ingnot, Ledwina, and Cmiel (2018) in order to more easily calculate it for two sets of tests, developed a pathwise variant that does not require specific sequences of alternative parameters. We shall introduce this variant referred to as the ILC i-ARE for this setting alongside that of K i-ARE.

In the final section, we propose a generalization of the K i-ARE and ILC i-ARE to quantum field regression testing statistics in the data censoring setting where a spectrum of quantum probabilities dependent on orthomodular lattices that dictate their respective statistical settings. These generalizations will then be applied to the universal hypothesis testing framework that is relevant to all statistical hypothesis testing settings and other uncertainty frameworks for probability regimes.

i-efficiency in nonparametric random field general regression with censoring

Let $(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{g}_t)$ be bivariate (M, L) random fields (RF) mapping to a measurable state space \mathcal{S} of dimension L , and $t \in \mathcal{T}$, where $\dim(\mathcal{T}) = M$ and acting on values from an m -dimensional Polish space \mathcal{X} . Consider a probability space $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{F}, \mu)$ where $\mathcal{F} \subseteq 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ is a σ -algebra of μ -measurable sets (events) in \mathcal{X} and μ a probability measure on \mathcal{F} . The generalized nonparametric random field regression problem is [10];

$$\mathbf{f}_t = m(\mathbf{g}_t, \epsilon_t) \quad (1)$$

where

$m(\mathbf{g}_t, \epsilon_t) = E(\mathbf{f}_t | \mathbf{g}_t = \mathbf{g}_t, \epsilon_t)$ is the generalized RF regression model function

\mathbf{f}_t is the dependent (M, L) RF of responses

$\mathbf{g}_t = \{\mathbf{g}_t^{(i)}\}$ is a K -vector of independent (M, L) RFs

ϵ_t is an error (M, L) RF

A special version of (1) is the simple additive error model;

$$\mathbf{f}_t = m(\mathbf{g}_t) + \sigma(\mathbf{g}_t)G(\epsilon_t) \quad (2)$$

where

$\sigma(\mathbf{g}_t)$ is the conditional variance of the RF \mathbf{f}_t given the random field \mathbf{g}_t

G a general function of ϵ_t

Note that both general linear regression and kernel regression are also special cases of (1).

We assume that $\epsilon_t \sim F(\cdot | \theta)$, defined on $(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{B}, \mu)$, and WLOG, $E(\epsilon_t) = \mathbf{0}_L$ and $\text{Var}(\epsilon_t) = \mathbf{1}_L$, and parameterized by $\theta = (\theta_j) \subset \Theta$ the distribution parameters from a multi-parameter space Θ . This very general form of nonparametric regression can be specialized for a nonparametric vector ARMA model taking $f_t = g_t$ in a leading time-indexed vector predictor.

Hypothesis testing in general regression problems most ostensibly come in two flavors;

1. Test for zero effects: $H_0 : \mathbf{f}_t = m(\mathbf{f}_{t_m}, \epsilon)$, $\mathbf{g}_{t_m} \subset \mathbf{g}_t$ vs. $H_a : \mathbf{f}_t = m(\mathbf{g}_t, \epsilon_t)$
2. Test of goodness-of-fit: $H_0 : \theta \in \Theta_0$ vs. $H_a : \theta \in \Theta_1 = \Theta \setminus \Theta_0$, where $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{f}_t - \hat{\mathbf{f}}_t \sim F(\theta)$, is the residual distribution, and $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_t = \hat{m}(\mathbf{g}_t)$ is the proposed model fitted value. Alternatively, one may look at a random field time series residual $\mathbf{e}_t = \mathbf{f}_t - \hat{\mathbf{f}}_t \sim F_t(\theta)$.

Test statistics will then be functions of the sample data of size N , $T_N((\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{g}_t))$ where the critical regions are given by extremal values $C_\kappa = \{(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{g}_t) : |T_N((\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{g}_t))| > \kappa\}$.

Now consider the case of censoring of random fields. Let \mathbf{c}_t be an independent random field representing the censoring times on the dependent random field observation \mathbf{f}_t and \mathbf{d}_t the independent random field representing censoring times on the independent random field \mathbf{g}_t . One then has the censored random fields expressed as;

$$\mathbf{f}_t^c = \mathbf{f}_t \wedge \mathbf{c}_t = \min(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{c}_t), \quad \mathbf{g}_t^d = \mathbf{g}_t \wedge \mathbf{d}_t = \min(\mathbf{g}_t, \mathbf{d}_t) \quad (3)$$

Here, the min functions are taken component-wise so that the results are (M, L) RFs. Now let $I_{\mathbf{c}_t^x} = I_{(\mathbf{f}_t^x \leq \mathbf{c}_t^x)}$ and $I_{\mathbf{d}_t^x} = I_{(\mathbf{g}_t^x \leq \mathbf{d}_t^x)}$ be the censoring indicator functions for the x -th d -dimensional random variable of the bivariate random fields respectively. One may denote the generalized censored random elements as $(\mathbf{f}_t^x, I_{\mathbf{c}_t^x})$ and $(\mathbf{g}_t^x, I_{\mathbf{d}_t^x})$. More generally, the c_t^x and d_t^x may be independently distributed random variables. In the more general setting, one may treat the \mathbf{c}_t^x and \mathbf{d}_t^x as μ -measurable sets from \mathcal{F} and denote the bivariate censored random variables as;

$$\mathbf{f}_t^c = \begin{cases} \mathbf{f}_t^x & \text{if } \mathbf{f}_t^x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \mathbf{c}_t^x \\ r(\mathbf{c}_t^x) & \text{if } \mathbf{f}_t^x \in \mathbf{c}_t^x \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_t^d = \begin{cases} \mathbf{g}_t^x & \text{if } \mathbf{g}_t^x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \mathbf{d}_t^x \\ h(\mathbf{d}_t^x) & \text{if } \mathbf{g}_t^x \in \mathbf{d}_t^x \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $r(\mathbf{c}_t^x), h(\mathbf{d}_t^x) : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ are appropriate real set functions on \mathcal{F} . Denote the censored bivariate random fields as $(\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)$.

Simple Type I censoring is the case where $\mathbf{c}_t^x = K, K \in \mathcal{S}$ and $\mathbf{d}_t^x = \infty, \forall x$.

Next, consider the hypothesis test for the goodness-of-fit of the generalized censored random field regression residuals $\mathbf{e}_t^c = \mathbf{f}_t^c - \hat{\mathbf{f}}_t^c \sim f(\theta)$;

$$H_0 : \theta \in \Theta_0 \text{ vs. } H_a : \theta \in \Theta_a \quad (6)$$

where $\Theta_0, \Theta_a \subset \Theta, \Theta_0 \cap \Theta_a = \emptyset$.

Theorem 1: Consider the subset of non-exponentially decreasing significance levels, α_N such that $\alpha_N \rightarrow 0$ and $\log \alpha_N = o(N)$ (as in the Bahadur efficiency). Let $\{\theta_N\} = \{(\theta_N^1, \dots, \theta_N^p)\} \subset \Theta$ be a sequence of distribution parameter vectors where P_θ is the corresponding probability measure to F_θ , such that;

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}} D(P_{\theta_N^x} \| P_{\theta_0^x}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}} ND^2(P_{\theta_N^x} \| P_{\theta_0^x}) = \infty \quad (8)$$

where D is a statistical distance between $P_{\theta_N^x}$ and $P_{\theta_0^x}$, w.r.t. μ and the index x , refers to points in the m -dimensional Polish space \mathcal{X} where the random fields act on and have the probability measures $P_{\theta_N^x}$ and $P_{\theta_0^x}$ as the null and alternative distributions respectively. Note that one may use any statistical distance such as the symmetric KL -divergence, α -Jenson-Shannon, Hellinger, or Bhattacharyya distances.

Denote the subspace of sequences in Θ satisfying (5) and (6) by $\mathcal{E} \subset \Theta$. Now consider a sequence of L test statistics each based on N samples and dependent on the censored random variables, $T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$, rejecting H_0 for large values; with critical regions $C_{\kappa_N^i} = \{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \kappa_N^i\}$.

Now let P_{θ_n} be the weighted product probability defined on Θ by:

$$P_{\theta_n} = \prod_{(i,j)}^{(N,M)} \zeta_{ij} P_{\theta_n}^{(ij)} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\sum_{(i,j)} \zeta_{ij} = 1 \quad (10)$$

Suppose that for any $\eta > 0, \exists$ positive functions $b^i(\theta) : \mathcal{P}_\Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ where \mathcal{P}_Θ is the space of probability distributions on Θ , such that for $\theta \in \Theta$ and $\{\theta_n\} \in \mathcal{E}$:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{\theta_n} \left(\left| \frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{b^i(\theta_n) \sqrt{n}} - 1 \right| \leq \eta \right) = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$- \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{nt_n^2} \right) \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_n} (T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > t_n \sqrt{n}) = 1 \quad (12)$$

for $t_n > o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\right)$ and $t_n = o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{n}}\right)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and the limit;

$$e_{i,j} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{b^i(\theta_n)}{b^j(\theta_n)} \right)^2 < \infty \quad (13)$$

for a pair of statistical tests $(T_N^{(i)}, T_N^{(j)})$ exists. Then the K i -ARE of $T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$ w.r.t. $T_N^j((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$ exists and is $e_{i,j}$.

If in (13) $t_n = o\left(\frac{\log n}{\sqrt{n}}\right)$ (resp. $t_n = o(1)$) then $e_{i,j} = e_{i,j}^w$ (resp. $e_{i,j} = e_{i,j}^s$) is the *weak* (resp. *strong*) K i -ARE.

Note that the b^i are explicit functions of (x_i) and $\bar{\beta}$ since the θ_N are.

One can then make a pairwise comparison of two tests $T_N^j((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$ and $T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$, and in a set of tests $\{T_N^k((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))\}_{k=1, \dots, L}$, one may totally order using a preference operator \leq_e defined by the equivalence $e_{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)), T_N^j((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))} \leq 1 \iff T_N^j((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \leq_e T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$. One can then find a maximal i-efficient element within a subset of $\{T_N^k((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))\}_{k=1, \dots, L}$ whose tests possess another optimal test property such as LMP (locally most powerful).

A recent and popular variant of the calculation of the K i-ARE was proposed and expanded on by Ignot, Ledwina and Cmeil (2018)[4]. We refer to this variant as the ILC i-ARE. The ILC i-ARE attempts to place different, slightly more applicable emphasis on regularity conditions on the tests being compared while keeping the general form of the K i-ARE. We will expand on their differences later. First, we show the ILC i-ARE calculation under certain regularity conditions for the nonparametric generalized regression with censoring setting, when it exists.

Theorem 2: As in the K i-ARE case, we consider the subset of sub-exponentially decreasing significance levels α_N , as the sample size $N \rightarrow \infty$, through the conditions $\alpha_N \rightarrow 0$ and $\frac{\log \alpha_N}{N} \rightarrow 0$. Let $\{\theta_n\} = \{(\theta_n^1, \dots, \theta_n^p)\} \subset \Theta$ and $T_N^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$ be a sequence of parameter vectors and test statistics respectively as in Theorem 1. Define the weighted product probability on Θ as in (10).

For a pair of statistical tests $(T_N^{(i)}, T_N^{(j)})$, and for every $\eta > 0$, if \exists a positive constant $\kappa_{T_N^{(i)}} > 0$, such that \forall positive sequences $t_N > 0$, such that $t_N \rightarrow 0$, $Nt_N^2 \rightarrow \infty$ and \exists positive functions $b^i(p_\theta) : \mathcal{P}_\Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, where \mathcal{P}_Θ is the space of probability distributions on Θ , with $\{\theta_n\} \in \mathcal{E}$ and for every positive sequence $\{\nu_N\}$ where $\nu_N \rightarrow 0$ and $N\nu_N^p \rightarrow \infty$ for some $\rho \in [1, 2]$:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} P_{\theta_n} \left(\left| \frac{T_N^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{b^i(\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N)) \sqrt{N}} - 1 \right| \geq \eta \right) = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$- \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{Nt_N^2} \right) \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_N} \left(T_N^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > t_N \sqrt{N} \right) = \kappa_{T_N^{(i)}} \quad (15)$$

and \exists sequences $\{\nu_N\}, \{\lambda_N\}$ such that $1 \leq \nu_N < \lambda_N \leq N$, $\nu_N = o(\lambda_N)$, $\frac{Nt_N^2}{\lambda_N} \rightarrow 0$, and $\frac{Nt_N^2}{\nu_N} \rightarrow \infty$, such that

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} P_{\theta_N} \left(\left| \frac{T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{b^j(\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N)) \sqrt{N}} - 1 \right| \geq \eta \right) = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$- \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{Nt_N^2} \right) \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_N} \left(T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > t_N \sqrt{N} \right) = \kappa_{T_N^{(j)}} \quad (17)$$

then, when it exists;

$$e_{T_N^{(i)}, T_N^{(j)}} = \frac{\kappa_{T_N^{(j)}} b^j(\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N))}{\kappa_{T_N^{(i)}} b^i(\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N))} \in [0, \infty] \quad (18)$$

is the ILC i-ARE of $T_N^{(j)}$ with respect to $T_N^{(i)}$.

The quantity $m(T_N^{(k)}) = \kappa_{T_N^{(k)}} b^k(\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N))$ was referred to by ILC as the intermediate slope of $T_N^{(k)}$ under $\mathbb{P}_{\nu_N}^M(\theta_N)$ and the quantity $\kappa_{T_N^{(k)}}$ as its index of moderate deviation.

Proof of Theorem 1: let $\{\alpha_n\}$ be a sequence of significance levels \ni

$$\alpha_n = o(1) \quad (19)$$

$$- \log \alpha_n = o\left(\sqrt[3]{N}\right) \quad (20)$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Let $\{\theta_N\}$ be a sequence of alternatives satisfying conditions (5) and (6). Additionally, we assume that the power function of ϕ_N^i , the α_n -level test based on the statistic $T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$, are bounded away from 0, so that

$$0 < \liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} E_{\theta_N}(\phi_N^i) \leq \limsup_{N \rightarrow \infty} E_{\theta_N}(\phi_N^i) \quad (21)$$

Let $\kappa_N = t_N^i \sqrt{\sqrt[3]{N}}$ denote the critical value of ϕ_N^i so that

$$\kappa_N = \inf_d \left\{ \sup_{\theta_N \in \Theta_a} P_{\theta_N}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > d) \leq \alpha_N \right\} \quad (22)$$

One then has the condition;

$$\sup_{\theta \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i(\mathbf{Y}, \bar{\delta}) > \kappa_N) \leq \alpha_N < \sup_{\theta \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \kappa), \forall \kappa < \kappa_N \quad (23)$$

Now, consider the sequence,

$$\delta_N = \sqrt{-\frac{2 \log \alpha_N}{\sqrt[3]{N}}} \quad (24)$$

Since $-\log \alpha_N = o(\sqrt[3]{N})$, then $\delta_N = o(1)$. Define $t_N = \delta_N \sqrt[3]{N}$. Then $t_N \sqrt{\sqrt[3]{N}} \rightarrow \infty$ and $t_N \sqrt[3]{N} \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$, so condition (10) can be applied to $\{t_N\}$, yielding;

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{\log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \delta_N \sqrt[6]{N})}{2 \log \alpha_N} \right] = 1 \quad (25)$$

implying

$$\sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \delta_N \sqrt[6]{N}) < \alpha_N \quad (26)$$

so that $\delta_N \sqrt[6]{N} \geq \kappa_N$ or $\frac{\delta_N}{\sqrt[3]{N}} \geq t_N^i$ for large enough N . Since $\delta_N = o(1)$ then $t_N^i = o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{N}}\right)$ and condition (10) can be applied to $\{t_N^i\}$.

Now fix $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Then $\exists l \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \ni t_N \sqrt{\sqrt[3]{N}} > a$, for $N > l$ and by condition (10) $\exists \epsilon(l) > 0 \ni$,

$$-\frac{\log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq a)}{N t_N^2} > 1 - \epsilon(l) \quad (27)$$

for $N > l$.

One then has that,

$$\liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq a) > -\infty \quad (28)$$

so that

$$\sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq a) > 0, \forall a \in \mathbb{R} \quad (29)$$

Now $0 \leq \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq \kappa_N) \leq \alpha_N \rightarrow 0 \implies$

$$\sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0}(T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq \kappa_N) \rightarrow 0 \quad (30)$$

so $\kappa_N \rightarrow \infty$.

By condition (9), one has that,

$$\frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N} b_i(\theta_N)} \xrightarrow{P_{\theta_N}} 1 \quad (31)$$

By condition (10) applied to $\{t_N^i\}$;

$$\frac{-\log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} \left(\frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N}} \geq t_N \right)}{N t_N^2} \rightarrow 1, \text{ as } t_N \sqrt{N} \rightarrow \infty \quad (32)$$

so that;

$$-\log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} \left(\frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N}} \geq t_N \right) \rightarrow -\infty \text{ as } t_N \rightarrow \infty \quad (33)$$

and so;

$$\sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} \left(\frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N}} \geq t_N \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (34)$$

Let $\epsilon_N = \frac{t_N^i}{b^i(\theta_N)} - 1$. Then by (14), one has that;

$$0 < \liminf_{N \rightarrow \infty} P_{\theta_N} \left[\frac{T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{b^i(\theta_N)} \geq \epsilon_N + 1 \right] < 1 \quad (35)$$

So

$$t_N^i = b^i(\theta_N) (1 + o(1)), \text{ as } N \rightarrow \infty \quad (36)$$

Also by (14);

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} (T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq \kappa_N) \leq \log \alpha_N < & \log \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} (T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq \kappa) & \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ -N (t_N^i)^2 = -N b^i(\theta_N)^2 (o(1) + 1) & & -\infty \text{ (since } \kappa < \kappa_N = t_N^i \sqrt{N} \rightarrow \infty) \end{array}$$

so that;

$$\log \alpha_N = -N b^i(\theta_N)^2 (o(1) + 1) \quad (37)$$

Denote the following;

$$m_{\phi^i, \phi^j}(N) = \inf \left\{ r : E_{\theta_N} (\phi_{r+n; \alpha_N}^j) \geq E_{\theta_N} (\phi_{N; \alpha_N}^i), \forall n = 0, 1, \dots \right\} \quad (38)$$

where $\phi_{N; \alpha}^i$ is the level α test based on the statistic $T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))$. By definition;

$$\text{i-efficiency of } T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \text{ w.r.t. } T_N^j((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) = e_{\phi^i, \phi^j} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m_{\phi^i, \phi^j}(N)}{N} \quad (39)$$

Now let $\{\gamma_j\}$ be any sequence in \mathbb{R} such that

$$e < \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \gamma_j \leq \infty \quad (40)$$

and $\{N_j\}$ be any sequence in \mathbb{N} such that

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} N_j \rightarrow \infty \quad (41)$$

and such that

$$\gamma_1 N_1 < \gamma_2 N_2 < \dots \quad (42)$$

with $\gamma_j N_j \in \mathbb{N}, j = 1, \dots$

We will show that

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{\gamma_j N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^i = 1 \quad (43)$$

Assuming (36) and that $\gamma_j N_j > e N_j = m(N_j)$, for $j > m$, one can conclude

$$E_{\theta_N} \phi_{m(N)-1; \alpha_N}^j < E_{\theta_N} \phi_{N; \alpha_N}^i \quad (44)$$

implying that

$$0 < \sup E_{\theta_N} \phi_{m(N)-1; \alpha_N}^j < E_{\theta_N} \phi_{N; \alpha_N}^i < 1, \forall N \quad (45)$$

Since $\gamma_j N_j > m(N_j)$, one has that;

$$0 < E_{\theta_N} \phi_{m(N_j)-1; \alpha_{N_j}}^j < E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^i \leq E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{\gamma_j N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^j < 1 \quad (46)$$

Then $E_{\theta_N} \phi_{m(N_j)-1; \alpha_{N_j}}^j \rightarrow 1$, since $E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{\gamma_j N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^j \rightarrow 1$. This implies

$$\limsup_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m(N_j)}{N_j} = \limsup_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m(N_j) - 1}{N_j} \quad (47)$$

Now,

$$\frac{m(N_j) - 1}{N_j} \leq e, \forall j \implies \limsup_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m(N_j) - 1}{N_j} \leq e \quad (48)$$

So from (40) and (41) one obtains

$$\limsup_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m(N_j)}{N_j} \leq e \quad (49)$$

We return to proving (36). To apply condition (9) of the theorem to the sequence $\frac{T_N^j}{N}(\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d) \sqrt{N} b^{(j)}(\theta_N)$, we introduce a subsequence of alternatives $\{\theta_N^*\}$ as follows,

$$\theta_N^{(k)*} = \begin{cases} \theta_{N_j}^{(k)} & \text{if } N = \gamma_j N_j, \text{ for some } j \\ \theta_N^{(k)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

for $k = 1, \dots, p$.

Then

$$\liminf_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} \sup_{1 \leq k \leq p} H(\theta_N^{(k)*}, \theta_0^{(k)}) = 0 \quad (51)$$

$$\liminf_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} \sup_{1 \leq k \leq p} N H^2(\theta_N^{(k)*}, \theta_0^{(k)}) = \infty \quad (52)$$

Make a change of notation for convenience as follows, let $N = \alpha_j N_j$ and let $\kappa_N^{(j)} = \sqrt{N_j} t_{N_j}^{(j)}$ be the critical value of $\phi_{\alpha_{N_j}}^{(j)}$, so that;

$$\sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} \left(T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \kappa_N^{(j)} \right) \leq \alpha_{N_j} < \sup_{\theta_0 \in \Theta_0} P_{\theta_0} \left(T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) \geq \kappa \right) \quad (53)$$

for $\kappa > \kappa_N^{(j)}$.

As before, one can show that

$$\kappa_{N_j}^{(j)} \rightarrow \infty \text{ and } t_{N_j}^{(j)} = o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{N}}\right) \quad (54)$$

and that

$$-\frac{\log \alpha_{N_j}}{N \left(t_{N_j}^{(j)}\right)^2} \rightarrow 1 \text{ or } \log \alpha_{N_j} = -N \left(t_{N_j}^{(j)}\right)^2 (1 + o(1)) \text{ as } j \rightarrow \infty \quad (55)$$

By (11), (30) and (48), one has that;

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{t_{N_j}^{(j)}}{b^{(j)}(\theta_{N_j})} \right]^2 = \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N \left(t_{N_j}^{(j)} \right)^2}{N_j b^{(i)}(\theta_{N_j})^2} \left[\frac{b^{(i)}(\theta_{N_j})}{b^{(j)}(\theta_{N_j})} \right] \frac{N_j}{N} \quad (56)$$

$$= e \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\gamma_j} < 1 \quad (57)$$

since γ_j is bounded away from $e > 0$.

Now $\bar{\theta}_{\gamma_j N_j}^* = \bar{\theta}_{N_j}^*, \forall j$. Hence;

$$E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{\gamma_j N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^{(j)} \geq P_{\theta_{N_j}} \left(T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \frac{\sqrt{N} t_{N_j}^{(j)}}{\kappa_N^{(j)}} \right) \quad (58)$$

The events $\left[T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) > \sqrt{N} t_{N_j}^{(j)} \right]$ and $\left[\frac{T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N} b^{(j)}(\theta_N^*)} > \frac{t_{N_j}^{(j)}}{b^{(j)}(\theta_{N_j}^*)} \right]$ are equivalent. So by (49) one has that;

$$\lim_{j \in \mathcal{J}} P_{\theta_{N_j}} \left(\frac{T_N^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N} b^{(j)}(\theta_N^*)} > \frac{t_{N_j}^{(j)}}{b^{(j)}(\theta_{N_j}^*)} \right) > \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} P_{\theta_{N_j}} \left(1 - \epsilon \leq \frac{T^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N} b^{(j)}(\theta_N)} \leq 1 + \epsilon \right) \quad (59)$$

for every $\epsilon > 0$.

By (9), one then has that;

$$1 > E_{\theta_{N_j}} \phi_{\gamma_j N_j; \alpha_{N_j}}^{(j)} \geq P_{\theta_{N_j}} \left(1 - \epsilon \leq \frac{T^{(j)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d))}{\sqrt{N} b^{(j)}(\theta_N)} \leq 1 + \epsilon \right) \rightarrow 1 \quad (60)$$

Hence (36) has been shown to be true so that (42) holds, that is;

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sup \frac{m(N)}{N} \leq e \quad (61)$$

Using similar arguments with inf replaced by sup and \geq replaced with \leq , one obtains;

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \inf \frac{m(N)}{N} \geq e \quad (62)$$

Using (54) and (55) immediately implies

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{m(N)}{N} = e \quad \square \quad (63)$$

As a special case and to make the calculation of the i-efficiency clearer, we consider the following adaptation from the Pitman approach and as shown by Kallenberg for the univariate parameter case;

Corollary: Let $\Theta = (\mathbb{R}^+)^p$, $\Theta_0 = \{\bar{\theta}_0\}$, and $\Theta_1 = \Theta \setminus \Theta_0$ be the parameter spaces for our testing problem. Suppose \exists functions $\mu^{(i)} : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\sigma^{(i)} : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that;

$$D_{(j)}^+ \mu^{(i)}(\theta_0) > 0, j = 1, \dots, p \quad (64)$$

where $D_{(j)}^+ \equiv \frac{\partial^+}{\partial \theta^{(j)}}$ is the right-side partial derivative w.r.t. $\theta^{(j)}$, that is, $\nabla^+ \mu^{(i)}(\theta_0) \in [\mathbb{R}^+ \setminus \{\theta_0\}]^p$ or as a directional derivative;

$$(i) \quad 0 < \nabla^+ \mu(\theta_0) \bar{\mathbf{1}}_i^T, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, p \quad (65)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{1}}_i$ is the vector of dimension N with all zeros except an entry 1 in the i -th position, and

$$(ii) \quad \lim_{\bar{\theta} \rightarrow \bar{\theta}_0} \sigma^{(i)}(\theta_0) > 0, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2 \quad (66)$$

Then if;

$$(a) \frac{P \left[\frac{\sqrt{N} \left(U_n^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) - \mu^{(i)}(\theta_0) \right)}{\sigma^{(i)}(\theta_0)} \right]}{1 - \Phi(x_n)} = 1 + o(1) \quad (67)$$

for $0 < x_n < o(\sqrt[6]{n})$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and

$$(b) P_{\theta_n} \left[\frac{\sqrt{n} U_n^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) - \mu^{(i)}(\theta_n)}{\sigma^{(i)}(\theta_n)} < x \right] \rightarrow \Phi(x) \quad (68)$$

for $\max_{1 \leq j \leq p} \theta_n^{(j)} = o(1)$ and $\min_{1 \leq j \leq p} \theta_n^{(j)} > o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\right)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and

$$(c) \text{ for a sequence } \{\theta_n\} \subset \Theta \text{ such that;} \quad (69)$$

$$(i) \sup_{1 \leq j \leq p} H(\theta_n^{(j)}, \theta_0^{(j)}) \rightarrow 0 \iff \max_{1 \leq j \leq p} \theta_n^{(j)} \rightarrow 0 \quad (70)$$

and

$$(ii) \max_{1 \leq j \leq p} H(\theta_n^{(j)}, \theta_0^{(j)}) = a\theta^{(j)^2} + b \text{ as } \theta^{(j)} \rightarrow \theta_0^{(j)} \quad (71)$$

for some $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, such that $a > 0, b = o(\theta^{(j)^2})$, and

$$\left[\frac{\|\nabla^+ \mu^1(\theta_0)\| \sigma^{(2)}(\theta_0)}{\|\nabla^+ \mu^1(\theta_0)\| \sigma^{(1)}(\theta_0)} \right]^2 = e < \infty \quad (72)$$

then

$$e = e_{\bar{U}^{(1)}, \bar{U}^{(2)}} \quad (73)$$

is the i-efficiency of $\bar{U}^{(1)}$ and $\bar{U}^{(2)}$, where $\bar{U}^{(i)} = (\tilde{U}_1^{(i)}, \tilde{U}_2^{(i)}, \dots)$ are the statistics that are rejecting the null hypothesis for large values.

If $o(\sqrt[6]{n})$ in condition (60) is replaced by $O(\sqrt{\log n})$ or $o(\sqrt{n})$ respectively, then $e = e_{\bar{U}^{(1)}, \bar{U}^{(2)}}^w$ and $e = e_{\bar{U}^{(1)}, \bar{U}^{(2)}}^s$ are the weak and strong efficiencies respectively of $\bar{U}^{(1)}$ and $\bar{U}^{(2)}$.

Proof. Using the test statistics and normalizing functions;

$$T_N^i((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) = \frac{U_N^{(i)}((\mathbf{f}_t^c, \mathbf{g}_t^d)) - \mu^{(i)}(\bar{\theta}_0)}{\frac{\sigma^{(i)}(\theta_0)}{\sqrt{2N}}} \quad (74)$$

$$b^{(i)}(\theta_0) = \frac{\mu^{(i)}(\theta) - \mu^{(i)}(\theta_0)}{\frac{\sigma^{(i)}(\theta_0)}{\sqrt{2}}} \quad (75)$$

we obtain the following from conditions of the theorem;

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{b^{(1)}(\theta_n)}{b^{(2)}(\theta_n)} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\mu^{(1)}(\theta_N) - \mu^{(2)}(\theta_0)}{\mu^{(2)}(\theta_N) - \mu^{(1)}(\theta_0)} \quad (76)$$

$$= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{\nabla \mu^{(1)}(\theta_N - \theta_0)(\theta_N - \theta_0) + o(\|\theta_N - \theta_0\|)}{\nabla \mu^{(2)}(\theta_N - \theta_0)(\theta_N - \theta_0) + o(\|\theta_N - \theta_1\|)} \right] \frac{\sigma^{(2)}(\theta_0)}{\sigma^{(1)}(\theta_0)} \quad (77)$$

$$= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{\nabla \mu^{(1)}(\theta_0)(\theta_N - \theta_0)}{\nabla \mu^{(2)}(\theta_0)(\theta_N - \theta_1)} \right] \frac{\sigma^{(2)}(\theta_0)}{\sigma^{(1)}(\theta_0)} \quad (78)$$

The limit exists since the $\mu^{(i)}$ are differentiable on $\bigotimes_{i=1}^p \Theta_i$. \square

We use the corollary to calculate the regular i-efficiency of linear rank statistics based on the generalized

Prentice rank and a typical MLE test statistic for the censoring scheme.

Consider the simple linear rank statistic for the general linear regression with censoring [5];

$$S_N(\bar{\varphi}) = \sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i} a_N(R_{N_i}, \delta_{N_i}) \quad (79)$$

where (R_{N_i}, δ_{N_i}) is the Peto-Prentice censored generalized rank.

Specifically, we write;

$$R_{N_i} = \sum_{k=1}^N u(w_i - w_k) \delta_{N_k} \quad (80)$$

where u is the Heavyside function and $w_i = y_i - \theta^{(i)}$, the i -th residual observed. Also, $\bar{\varphi} = (\varphi_0, \varphi_1)$ where φ_i is the score generating function defining the a_N as;

$$a_N(i, j) = E[\varphi_j(U_{n,i})] \quad (81)$$

$$= \varphi_j\left(\frac{i}{n+1}\right) \quad (82)$$

for $j = 0, 1$ where $U_{n,i}$ is the i -th order statistic for the uniformly distributed random variable $U_n \sim U(0, 1)$.

Assume WLOG. that;

$$\sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i} = 1, \quad \sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i}^2 = 1 \quad (83)$$

$$\max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |x_{N_i}| \leq \frac{A_1}{\sqrt[3]{n}}, \quad \sum_{i=1}^N |x_{N_i}|^3 \leq \frac{A_2}{\sqrt{n}}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2 \quad (84)$$

where $A_1, A_2 > 0$ are constants, and

$$\max_{j=0,1} \max_{1 < i \leq n-1+j} \left| a_n(i, j) - \varphi_j\left(\frac{i}{n+1}\right) \right| \leq \frac{A_3}{(\sqrt{n})^\delta} \quad (85)$$

for some constant $A_3 > 0, n \geq 2$, and constant $\delta, 0 < \delta \leq 1$.

We place the following conditions on $\bar{\varphi}$;

- (a) φ_1 is monotonic on $(0, 1)$
- (b) $\int_0^1 \varphi_1(u) du = 0$
- (c) $|\varphi_1(u) - \varphi_1(v)| \leq A_4 |u - v|^\delta, \forall u, v \in (0, 1)$ where $A_4 > 0$, a constant
- (d) $\varphi_0(u) = \begin{cases} \frac{\int_u^1 \varphi_1(v) dv}{(1-u)}, & 0 \leq u < 1 \\ \lim_{v \rightarrow 1^-} \varphi_0(v), & u = 1 \end{cases}$
- (e) $\frac{\partial \varphi_i(u)}{\partial u} \neq 0$ on $[0, 1]$ a. s.

We compute the location and scale functions of $S_N(\bar{\varphi})$ as follows;

Let;

$$\hat{\sigma}_N^2(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i}^2 \int_0^1 [\varphi_{\delta_{N_i}}(F_\theta(x_{N_i})) - \bar{\varphi}_{\delta_{N_i}}]^2 dF_\theta(x_{N_i}) \quad (86)$$

be the rank statistic scale parameter function and

$$\mu_n(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i} \int_0^1 \varphi_{\delta_{N_i}}(F_\theta(x_{N_i})) dF_\theta(x_{N_i}) \quad (87)$$

the location parameter function.

Under a more general random censoring case, [2] has shown that;

$$T_N(\bar{\varphi}) = \frac{S_N(\bar{\varphi}) - \mu_N(\bar{\varphi})}{\hat{\sigma}_N^2(\bar{\varphi})} \underset{\text{a.s.}}{\sim} N(0, 1) \quad (88)$$

Note that under our conditions on the scores;

$$\hat{\sigma}_N^2(\theta_0) = \|\varphi_1\|_2^2 - \int_{\bar{\delta}_N} [\varphi_1(u) - \varphi_0(F(u))]^2 du = 0 \quad (89)$$

$$\mu_N(\theta_0) = 0 \quad (90)$$

where $\bar{\delta}_N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \delta_{N_i}}{N}$. [11] has shown a Cramer-type large deviation result for $T_N(\bar{\varphi})$ under H_0 with Θ_0 (as well as weak convergence results). Specifically, these were shown for Type I censoring;

$$\sup_{x \in I_N} \left| \frac{1 - G_N(x)}{1 - \Phi(x)} - 1 \right| = o(1), \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \quad (91)$$

where $I_N = (0, \rho_N N^{\frac{\delta}{6}})$, $\{\rho_N\}$ a sequence such that $\phi_N = o(1)$ and $T_N(\bar{\varphi}) \sim G_N$. This result is stronger than our large deviation assumption in the Corollary. We impose convergence criteria on the sequence $\{\bar{\theta}_N\}$ of alternatives and the distributions F_{N_i} under H_0 ;

1. $\max_{1 \leq j \leq p} H(\theta_k^{(j)}, 0) \rightarrow \infty \iff \max_{1 \leq j \leq p} \theta_n^{(j)} \rightarrow 0$
2. $\max_{1 \leq j \leq p} H(\theta_k^{(j)}, 0) a \theta^{(j)^2} + b$ as $\theta^{(j)} \rightarrow 0$, for some $a > 0$, and $b = o(\theta^{(j)^2})$

In particular, we write $f_{N_i}(x_{N_i}) = F_\theta^{N_i}(x_{N_i})$ for the regression problem. The cumulative distribution for all samples x_{N_i} is;

$$H_N(\bar{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N F_\theta^{(N_i)}(x_{N_i}) \quad (92)$$

then if $\frac{\partial F_\theta}{\partial \theta}$ exists on $(0, 1)$ and \exists a function f such that;

1. $\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{\partial F_\theta}{\partial \theta} = f, \quad F_\theta \text{ a.e.}$
2. $\left| \frac{\partial \varphi_{\delta_{N_i}}}{\partial \theta} \right| \leq h_i, \quad F_\theta \text{ a.e. for some function } h_i, F_\theta^{(N_i)}, i = 1, \dots, N$
3. $\int_0^1 \frac{\partial \varphi_{\delta_{N_i}}}{\partial \theta}(F_0) f dF_0 > 0,$

then the interchange of derivative and integral for μ_N w.r.t. $\bar{\theta}$ can be done. It follows that one can write;

$$\frac{\partial \mu_N(\theta)}{\partial \theta} = \sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i} w_{N_i} dF_\theta^{(N_i)}(x_{N_i}) \quad (93)$$

where

$$w_{N_i} = \sum x_{N_i} E[\varphi(x_{N_i}, \delta_{N_i})] = E[E[(\varphi, \delta_{N_i}) | \delta_{N_i}]] \quad (94)$$

One can then form the efficacy of $S_N(\bar{\varphi})$;

$$c_{S_N(\bar{\varphi})}^2 = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i} w_{N_i} \right]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N x_{N_i}^2 \int_0^1 \left[\varphi_{\delta_{N_i}} \left(F_{\bar{\theta}}^{(N_i)}(x_{N_i}) \right) - \varphi_{\bar{\delta}_{N_i}} \right]^2 dF_{\bar{\theta}}^{(N_i)}(x_{N_i})} \quad (95)$$

Now consider an MLE statistic for our regression problem. The most familiar parametric methods dealing with censored data in regression testing are based on likelihoods. These include partial, marginal, and conditional likelihoods of the Cox proportional hazards method. One may then choose a typical likelihood method for comparison. The complete likelihoods can be written as;

$$L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N) = \prod_{i:\delta_{N_i}=1} f_{\theta}(x_{N_i}) \prod_{i:\delta_{N_i}=0} (1 - F_{\theta}(x_{N_i})) \prod_{i:\delta_{N_i}=1} g_i(x_{N_i}) \prod_{i:\delta_{N_i}=0} (1 - G_i(x_{N_i})) \quad (96)$$

where the censoring times $C_i \sim g_i$ with cdf G_i . We can treat the last two products as constants w.r.t. $\bar{\theta}$ in this Type I censoring case.

The likelihood optimization problem;

$$\bar{\theta}_{MLE} \in \underset{\theta \in \Theta}{\operatorname{argmax}} L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N) \quad (97)$$

reduces to solving the system of equations for θ ;

$$0 = \nabla_{\theta} \log L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N) \quad (98)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^{(j)}} \log L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N) \quad (99)$$

$$= \sum_{i:\delta_{N_i}=1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^{(j)}} \log f_{\theta}(x_{N_i}) + \sum_{i:\delta_{N_i}=0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^{(j)}} \log (1 - F_{\theta}(x_{N_i})) \quad (100)$$

for $j=1, \dots, p$.

Let $G(\theta) = \nabla_{\theta} \log L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N)$ and $H(\theta) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^{(i)} \partial \theta^{(j)}} \log L_{\theta}(\tilde{x}_N)$ denote the gradient and Hessian respectively of $\log L_{\theta}$. The Newton-Raphson method gives the estimates;

$$\theta_{(i)} = \theta_{(i-1)} - H(\theta_{(i-1)})^{-1} G(\theta_{(i-1)}) \quad (101)$$

at the i -th iterate.

Let $\dot{\hat{\theta}}_0 = H(\hat{\theta}_0)$ denote the sample information matrix at $\hat{\theta}_0$. One then has that;

$$E(\dot{\hat{\theta}}_0) = -E(H(\hat{\theta}_0)) = I(\hat{\theta}_0) \quad (102)$$

the Fisher information matrix. Then $\dot{\hat{\theta}}_0$ is an unbiased estimator of $I(\theta_0)$.

The estimate;

$$\hat{\theta}_{(j)} = \hat{\theta}_{(j-1)} + I(\hat{\theta}_{(j-1)})^{-1} G(\hat{\theta}_{(j-1)}) \quad (103)$$

is then utilized after an adequate convergence criteria has been met.

For the null hypothesis $H_0 : \bar{\theta} = \theta_0$, we consider the test statistic based on likelihoods;

$$\hat{T}_N = \left[\hat{\theta}_N - \theta_0 \right]^T \underline{I}(\theta_0) \left[\hat{\theta}_N - \theta_0 \right] \underset{\text{a.s.}}{\sim} \chi^2(p) \quad (104)$$

under H_0 .

Efron and Hinkley [3] have suggested replacing $\underline{I}(\theta_0)$ with $\dot{\hat{\theta}}_0$ under censoring because of the difficulty in calculating $\underline{I}(\theta_0)$ under these circumstances. Moreover, $\dot{\hat{\theta}}_0$ may be replaced by $\dot{\hat{\theta}}_N$ yielding the test statistic;

$$\left[\hat{\theta}_N - \theta_0 \right]^T \dot{\hat{\theta}}_N \left[\hat{\theta}_N - \theta_0 \right] \quad (105)$$

Since

$$\underline{I}(\theta_0) \underline{i}(\theta_0)^{-1} \xrightarrow{\text{prob}} I_N \quad (106)$$

under H_0 , then $\hat{T}_N \underset{\text{a.s.}}{\sim} \chi^2(p)$ under H_0 .

Under the alternatives;

$$\hat{T}_N \underset{\text{a.s.}}{\sim} \chi^2(\delta^2) \quad (107)$$

where $\delta^2 = \delta^2(\theta) = \theta^T I(\theta)^{-1} \theta$ is the noncentrality parameter. It may be shown using characteristic functions that $\mu_N(\theta) = p + \delta^2(\theta)$ and $\sigma_N^2(\theta) = 2p + 4\delta^2(\theta)$ are the mean and variance of \hat{T}_N respectively, so that;

$$\frac{\hat{T}_N(\theta) - \mu_N(\theta)}{\sigma_N^2(\theta)} \underset{\text{a.s.}}{\sim} N(0, 1) \quad (108)$$

We now form its efficacy;

$$c_{\hat{T}_N}^2 = \frac{\|\nabla \mu_N(\theta)\|^2}{\sigma_N^2(\theta)} \quad (109)$$

$$= \frac{\|\nabla \delta^2(\theta)\|^2}{2(p + 2\delta^2(\theta))} \quad (110)$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta^{(i)}} [\theta^T I(\theta) \theta]_{\theta=\theta_0}}{2(p + 2\theta_0^T I(\theta_0)^{-1} \theta_0)} \quad (111)$$

and finally compute the regular i-efficiency of $S_N(\bar{\varphi})$ w.r.t. \hat{T}_N using (102) and (88);

$$e_{S_N(\bar{\varphi}), \hat{T}_N} = \frac{c_{S_N(\bar{\varphi})}^2}{c_{\hat{T}_N}^2} \quad (112)$$

The i-efficiency may be calculated in these situations utilizing Cramer-type large deviation results for linear rank statistics with Type I and random censoring data.

References

- [1] Prentice, R. L. (1978). Linear rank tests with right censored data. *Biometrika*, 65, 1, 167-179.
- [2] Cezick, J. (1985). Asymptotic properties of censored linear rank tests. *Annals of Statistics*, 3, 1, 133-141
- [3] Efron, B., and Hinkley, D. V. (1978). Assessing the accuracy of the maximum likelihood estimator. *Biometrika*, 65, 3, 457-482.
- [4] Inglot, T, Ledwina, T, and Cmiel, B. (2019). Intermediate efficiency in nonparametric testing problems with an application to some weighted statistics. *ESAIM*, 23, 697-738, 40, 6, 1880-1900.
- [5] Jureckova, J. (1985). Asymptotic linearity of a rank statistic in regression parameter. *The Annals of Statistics*, 40, 6, 1880-1900.
- [6] Kallenberg, W. C. M. (1985). Intermediate efficiency, theory and examples. *The Annals of Statistics*, 11, 1, 170-182.
- [7] Massri, C., Holik, F., and Plastino A. (2018). States in generalized probabilistic models: An approach based in algebraic geometry. *Math. Slovaca*, 69, 1, 53-70.
- [8] Nikitin, Y. (2009). Asymptotic efficiency of non-parametric tests. *Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, UK*.
- [9] Ould-Said, E., and Lemdani, M. (2006). Asymptotic properties of a nonparametric regression function estimator with randomly truncated data. *ISM*, 2006
- [10] Rivas-Martinez, G. I., and Jimenez-Gamero, M. D. (2016). Computationally efficient goodness-of-fit tests for the error distribution in nonparametric regression. *REVSTAT - Statistical Journal*, 16, 1, 137-166.
- [11] Wu, T.-J. (1986).